

A REVIEW OF ENERGY STORAGE COMPOSITE STRUCTURES WITH EMBEDDED LITHIUM-ION BATTERIES

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Keywords: Multifunctional, batteries, lithium-ion, CFRP

ABSTRACT

Recent published research studies into multifunctional composite structures with embedded lithium-ion batteries are reviewed in this paper. The energy storage device architectures used in these structures are split into three categories: pouch batteries, thin-film batteries and bicells. The manufacturing techniques used to fabricate energy storage composite structures with these different battery types are discussed. The mechanical properties and electrical performance of the structures with and without embedded lithium-ion batteries is compared. It was found that the energy storage composite structures can perform in both superior and inferior ways depending on numerous factors. These factors include the manufacturing method, materials used, structural design, and the bond between the embedded batteries and the surrounding composite structure.

1 INTRODUCTION

Reduced energy consumption and emissions are two of the major issues that several transportation industries have been striving to achieve in recent years. The use of lightweight composite materials instead of steel and aluminium for load-bearing structures is one of the proposed approaches used in addressing these concerns, particularly in the automotive industry. Carbon fibre reinforced polymer laminate (CFRP) is one type of composite material used to construct both automobile interiors and structural panels. Moreover, a new generation of electric vehicles (EVs) and hybrid vehicles are gaining popularity. These vehicles require much larger energy storage capability compared to conventional internal combustion vehicles. Multifunctional components that can carry mechanical loads and store electrical energy have the potential to tackle these two trends simultaneously.

Several reviews of multifunctional composite materials with energy storage have been published [1-8]. The focus of the majority of previous reviews was on structural power and structural capacitor composites, where the composite material itself acts as an energy storage device. The purpose of this review is to provide an overview of energy storage composite structures with embedded batteries. In these structures, both the composite material and the embedded Li ion battery system are used for load-bearing and the batteries are also used for energy storage. The three major types of energy storage composite structures with embedded batteries are reviewed. These are distinguished by battery type: lithium-ion (Li-ion) and lithium-ion polymer (LiPo) pouch batteries (Figure 1a); thin-film Li-ion batteries (Figure 1b); and Li-ion bicells. Li-ion and LiPo pouch batteries are of interest because of their high gravimetric and volumetric energy densities, as shown in Figure 2. In addition, they can provide relatively higher energy storage when compared to the other battery chemistries that have same weight or volume. Li-ion batteries also have some ability to carry mechanical loads, including through-thickness compression, in-plane unconfined compression, in-plane confined compression, punch indentation and three-point bending [9-11]. This review is separated in two parts. Firstly, the manufacturing methods are reviewed, and secondly, the mechanical properties and electrical performance of the energy storage composite structures are then reviewed.

Figure 1: (a) Lithium-ion polymer (LiPo) pouch battery and (b) thin-film Li-ion battery, from LiPol Battery Co. Ltd, China.

Figure 2: Gravimetric and volumetric energy density of various batteries, adapted from [12].

2 MANUFACTURE OF MULTIFUNCTIONAL COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

This section presents an overview of published research on the manufacturing methods used to produce multifunctional composite structures with embedded energy storage devices. The designs and configurations described vary depending on three factors; the size of the embedded batteries, the type of experiment performed, and the expected application of the structure. Nevertheless, the aim of all the structures is to simultaneously carry mechanical loads and store electrical energy to reduce overall system weight and increase structural and energy efficiencies.

2.1 Multifunctional composites with embedded Li-ion and LiPo batteries

This type of structure involves embedding Li-ion or LiPo pouch batteries into sandwich composites (see Figure 3a) or monolithic laminates (see Figure 3b). Many researchers embedded batteries within cut-outs in the core materials of a sandwich composite [13-24]. There have also been studies that embed batteries in ply cut-outs in laminate structures [13, 25]. Various fabrication methods have been used to manufacture energy storage composites with embedded batteries. The most common methods are wet hand-layup and vacuum assisted resin infusion. The advantage of these techniques is the lack of heat and excessive pressure that can adversely affect the embedded pouch batteries. The fabrication of sandwich composites with embedded batteries by wet layup has been successfully achieved with both multi-stage curing [16-24] and co-curing [13-15].

Figure 3: Energy storage composites with embedded Li-ion polymer batteries before manufacture (upper images) and after manufacture (lower X-ray CT images) for (a) sandwich panel and (b) laminate panel [13].

2.2 Multifunctional composites with embedded thin-film Li-ion batteries

Thin film batteries (TFBs) have been used by several researchers in energy storage composite structures [26-33]. TFBs typically have a thickness less than one millimetre and can be embedded into composite laminates without significant alteration to the material or structural design. TFBs can be more easily formed into complex shapes compared to pouch batteries [34], however, their capacity is significantly lower.

Composites with embedded TFBs have been fabricated using CFRP prepregs [26, 27] and glass fibred reinforced polymer (GFRP) prepregs [27]. TFBs are typically inserted between layers of prepreg material (see Figure 4). Kim et al. [28] attached TFBs to a solar cell using an inkjet printer before integrating the interconnected electronic laminate with CFRP prepregs. The laminates were cured at elevated temperature and pressure. Bonding laminates and TFBs with adhesives is also another manufacturing option. Layers of a flexible solar panels, a piezoelectric, TFB, an actuator, and a fibreglass substrate were bonded using two-part epoxy and Kapton® insulation to create an energy storage composite structure [29, 30]. Another combination consisting of a solar cell, a TFB, and many electronic layers has also been made in a composite laminate [31]. However, no detailed explanation of the manufacturing process was provided. Besides solar cells, TFBs have been combined with piezoceramics to fabricate self-charging composite laminate structures. In this case, a vacuum bag was used to apply the pressure during bonding of the piezoceramic, TFB and metal substrate using a two-part epoxy and Kapton® insulation [32, 33].

Figure 4: Energy storage composites laminates with an embedded TFB, adapted from [27].

2.3 Multifunctional composites with embedded Li-ion bicells

Li-ion bicells consist of three electrodes; a central electrode sandwiched between two other electrodes, as shown in Figure 5. Bicells can be manufactured into energy storage composite structures using two approaches. The first approach stacks units of bicells (Figure 5a) that are then vacuum sealed within either aluminium packaging or cured CFRP laminates (Figure 5b) [35-37]. The second approach employs stacked bicells within the core of a sandwich composite (Figure 6) [38]. The stacked bicells can be integrated in an existing core structure and then adhesively bonded the facesheets [39].

Figure 5: (a) Schematic of Li-ion bicells, adapted from [35-37]. (b) Li-ion bicells within a carbon weave pouch, adapted from [36, 37].

Figure 6: Vertical bicells and aluminium triangular corrugation used in the core of a sandwich composite, adapted from [38].

3 PERFORMANCE OF MULTIFUNCTIONAL COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

Embedding batteries within composite structures can alter the mechanical properties. However, it is desirable that the performance of multifunctional structures remain comparable to those without an energy storage system. In terms of electrical properties, it is desirable that the composite structure protects the embedded batteries during mechanical loading and that the batteries can still function after the application of loads. In this section, the mechanical properties of energy storage composite structures are reviewed. The effect of mechanical loads on the electrical performance of embedded batteries is also discussed. This section is divided according to the type of embedded battery.

3.1 Multifunctional composites with embedded Li-ion and LiPo batteries

Published studies into embedding Li-ion and LiPo pouch batteries in composite structures are summarised in Table 1. Embedding pouch batteries have been found to have varying effects on the mechanical properties of composite structures. The batteries can be considered as damage tolerant devices, since most studies found the embedded pouch batteries to be functional after the application of static and dynamic loads. Embedding pouch batteries has been found to typically increase the mechanical performance of sandwich composites and decrease the mechanical performance of composite laminates. However, the edgewise compression performance decreased for both sandwich composites and laminates with embedded pouch batteries. When pouch batteries are embedded into cut-outs in composite laminates and sandwich composites, the continuity of plies or core material is disrupted, and a geometric stress concentration can be introduced.

Material system	Property investigated	Effect on property	Reference
CFRP/PVC foam sandwich composite	Damping ratio	An increase up to 310% for bending mode II when LiPo batteries are placed at theoretical vibration nodal points.	[13]
	Coincidence frequency	Linear increase with the number of LiPo batteries embedded	
CFRP laminate	Damping ratio	An increase up to 220% for bending mode II when the batteries are placed at theoretical vibration nodal points.	[13]
	Coincidence frequency	Linear increase with the number LiPo batteries embedded.	
CFRP/PVC foam sandwich composite	Flexural strength	No noticeable change in flexural strength and modulus when one and two batteries are embedded.	[14, 15]
	Electrical performance	No degradation in the embedded battery performance (battery capacity and internal resistance).	
CFRP/SAN foam sandwich composite	Tensile strength	No change in average failure load.	[16]
	Flexural strength	No change in average failure load.	
	Edge-wise compressive strength	Average ultimate compressive strength is reduced by 50%.	
	Electrical performance	No change in batteries charge and discharge performance.	
CFRP/SAN foam sandwich composite	Flexural strength	Increase in bending stiffness for specimens with embedded batteries. Failure load increased only when the batteries are surrounded by CFRP.	[17]
CFRP/Aluminium honeycomb sandwich composite	Electrical performance	No notable degradation in battery performance (end of discharge voltage and internal resistance) after a random vibration test at 15g and 25g.	[18]
CFRP/Aluminium honeycomb sandwich composite	Battery durability	No electrical degradation of the embedded battery was found after a random vibration test at 7g.	[19]

CFRP/PMI foam sandwich composite	Battery durability	Space thermal vacuum environment has little influence on the electrical performance of the embedded batteries.	[20]
CFRP/PMI foam sandwich composite	Flexural strength	The bending stiffness reduced by 19.5% when the structure was adhesively bonded to the battery with epoxy, but the stiffness reduction was 45% for a structure that has no adhesive bonding with battery.	[21]
	Edge-wise compressive strength	The average failure load was reduced by 8.3%.	
	Battery durability	No notable degradation of the batteries was found under any loading conditions.	
CFRP laminate	Edge-wise compressive strength	Compression strength and modulus of was reduced significantly when batteries were embedded.	[25]
	Electrical performance	A small increase in internal resistance was observed after edge-wise compression loading. Battery capacity was not significantly changed.	

Table 1: Performance of energy storage composite structures with embedded Li-ion and LiPo pouch batteries.

3.2 Multifunctional composites with embedded thin-film Li-ion batteries

Previous studies on the of effects of embedding TFBs in composite structures are summarised in Table 2. It is evident that embedding TFBs in composite structures generally results in relatively small changes in the mechanical properties of the composite structure. While TFBs are durable enough to withstand the heat and pressure from composite manufacturing processes, they are typically adversely affected by mechanical loads.

Material system	Property investigated	Effect on property	Reference
CFRP laminate	Tensile strength	The multifunctional laminates have slightly better tensile Young's modulus and strength.	[26]
	Battery durability	No notable degradation in charge and discharge performance when the structure was loaded under tension up to 450 MPa (50% of tensile strength).	
CFRP & GFRP laminates	Battery durability	The embedded batteries retained performance after being co-cured with composites at 132°C and 517 kPa.	[27]
Self-charging CFRP laminate (Solar cell)	Battery durability	The battery performance degraded significantly loaded to 0.45% tensile strain. The capacity retention remained at around 25% and 15% when the strain was 0.45% and 0.6% respectively.	[28]
Self-charging laminate (Solar cell)	Battery durability	The laminate remained functional after exposure to temperature variations between -80°C and 80°C and return to room temperature. However, a notable drop in voltage occurred at -40°C and eventually	[31]

		became critical at around -50°C.	
Self-charging laminate (Piezoceramics)	Flexural strength	Both piezoceramics and TFB layers are in critical conditions after flexural loading.	[32, 33]
	Battery durability	No mechanical or electrical failure was observed after the battery was dynamically loaded with a 7g excitation.	

Table 2: Performance of energy storage composite structures with embedded thin-film Li-ion batteries.

3.3 Multifunctional composites with embedded Li-ion bicells

Bicell units are typically stacked into layers before use. The number of stacks and the material of the pouch determined according to the application. Hence, the results of embedding bicells into composite materials can vary significantly, as shown in Table 3. So far, no trend has yet been set for the effects of embedding bicells.

Material system	Property investigated	Effect on property	Reference
CFRP/bicells sandwich composites	Numerical stiffness and strength index	For a carbon-weave reinforced structure, the stiffness and strength were reduced by about 43% and 73%, respectively. The carbon-epoxy composite experienced a 35% reduction in both stiffness and strength.	[36, 37]
Aluminium/bicells sandwich composites	Numerical shear modulus	The proposed designs had similar values of shear modulus in x-z and y-z planes as that of conventional honeycomb cores.	[38]
Aluminium/bicells sandwich composites	Natural frequency	The multifunctional sandwich composite exhibits similar or improved first natural frequency value compared to conventional honeycomb used in space applications.	[39]

Table 3: Performance of energy storage composite structures with embedded Li-ion bicells.

4 CONCLUDING REMARKS

Embedding batteries in composite structures can have different effects on the mechanical properties on the material. Changes to the mechanical properties arise from several factors, such as the manufacturing method, types of materials used, and the structural design. The bond between the embedded battery and the surrounding composite is also a factor. Energy storage composite structures can experience a reduction in mechanical properties if embedded batteries are not bonded in a way that allows efficient load transfer between the energy storage device and the surrounding composite structure. The performance of the embedded batteries is found to be outstanding, particularly for embedded Li-ion and LiPo pouch batteries, which are typically functional after the application of mechanical loads. Li-ion TFBs can survive the elevated temperatures and pressures used in some composite manufacturing process and the random vibration environment of a spacecraft launch. However, the performance of embedded Li-ion batteries is generally adversely affected by mechanical loads.

Impact damage tolerance, fatigue performance and long-term environmental durability are yet to be addressed in energy storage composite structures with embedded batteries. Moreover, only a few studies chose to embed multiple batteries into composites structures. This leads to a lack of information on these systems in terms of both mechanical properties and manufacturing processes. In addition, further finite element models would aid in predicting the performance and optimising the structure and device design.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The work was funded by the Australian Research Council (Grant Number IC160100032) as part of the ARC Training Centre in Lightweight Automotive Structures. The authors acknowledge the support of the Ford Motor Company.

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